

3D PRINTING AND IN-SITU THERMAL CURING OF CONTINUOUS FIBER-REINFORCED THERMOSET COMPOSITES

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Outline

- Challenges in composite manufacturing
- Additive manufacturing of composite materials
- Composite printing using thermoresponsive thermoset resin
 - Discontinuous fiber composites
 - Continuous fiber composites
- Conclusions

Challenges in Composite Manufacturing

Boeing autoclave

Heated mold for manufacturing a wind blade

Challenges in Composite Manufacturing

Subtractive Tooling Manufacturing

Additively Manufactured Tooling

Additive Manufacturing of Composites

Liu et al., *Materials and Design*, 2018

Clarkson et al., *Journal of Ceramic Materials*, 2022

Thermoplastic matrix:

- Poor thermomechanical properties
- Limited fiber content
- Large void content

Photocuring:

- Poor mechanical properties
- Limited fiber content
- Require post-curing steps, especially for carbon fiber composites

Printing via Frontal Polymerization

- Self-propagating cure mechanism driven by heat of polymerization
- Enables printing in air without additional stimulus

- Low printing speeds (<10 cm/min)
- Sensitive to ambient conditions
- Requires heated bed for sustained curing
- Limited fiber volume content

8X

1 cm

Ink Rheology

- Printing composites via direct ink writing (DIW) technique

Shear-Thinning Material

High Moduli for Shape Retention

Minimal Change in Viscosity

Discontinuous Fiber Composite Printing

5X

1 cm

Discontinuous Fiber Composites

4X

1 cm

Rapid Printing of Continuous Fiber Composites

Layer-by-Layer Printing of Continuous Fiber Composites

8X

Characterization

- Degree of cure exceeds 95% at speeds up to 1.5 m/min
- Fiber volume fraction > 50% and void content < 1.5%

Conclusions

- We developed a novel technique for printing thermoset polymer composites
- *In-situ* rapid curing allows for in-air printing without using support materials
- Ability to print discontinuous and continuous fiber composites at speeds up to 1.5 m/min
- High quality composites with a high volume-fraction of carbon fibers ($> 50\%$) and a low void content ($< 1.5\%$)
- No post cure required